

Synthesis and characterisation of triazolo- and pyrazol-3-yl quinoxaline derivatives from dehydro-L-ascorbic acid hydrazone and their antimicrobial activity

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Manuscript received 08 February 2018, revised 14 February 2018, accepted 29 May 2018

The 4-(pyrazol-3-yl)[1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-*a*]quinoxaline derivatives **4a-c** were prepared by the reaction of 2-chloro-3-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline **2** with arylhydrazines in ethanol followed by boiling the resulted products in butanol. Acetylation of **4a-c** with boiling acetic anhydride, afforded the acetyl derivatives **5a-c**. Treatment of **2** with thiosemicarbazide, afforded the quinoxaline hydrazinothiosemicarboxamide **6** which upon acetylation with boiling acetic anhydride, gave (1,2-dihydro-3-methyl-5*H*-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-3-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline **7**. Compound **2** reacted with sodium methoxide or sodium ethoxide, to produce the alkoxy derivatives **8a,b**. Furthermore, treatment of **2** with hydrazine hydrate, gave the 2-hydrazino derivative **9** which upon treatment with arylaldehydes, gave the arylhydrazones **10a-e** which were transformed to 1-aryl-4-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-*a*]quinoxalines **11a-c** and acetylated to **12a-c** compound **9** which when reacted with β -naphthylglyoxal produced **13**. It was also acetylated to **14**. Similarly, compound **9** reacted with ethylacetoacetate giving **15** and was acetylated to **16**. Some of the novel quinoxaline derivatives were subjected to *in vitro* antimicrobial screening.

Keywords: Dehydro-L-ascorbic acid, triazole, pyrazole, quinoxaline, antimicrobial.

Introduction

Dehydro-L-ascorbic acid, obtained by mild oxidation of L-ascorbic acid, is considered an excellent precursor for the synthesis of many nitrogen and sulphur heterocycles through its reactions with hydrazines or diamines. Dehydro-L-ascorbic acid has two carbonyl groups of different reactivity. This enable us to synthesise mono-, bis- and mixed bishydrazones. In addition, pyrazole nucleus and quinoxalines have pronounced pharmacological applications as anti-anxiety^{1,2}, antipyretic, analgesic and anti-inflammatory drugs³. Certain pyrazoles show significant bacteriostatic activity⁴. From these observations and in continuation of our work for the synthesis of heterocyclic compounds from dehydro-L-ascorbic acid and its analogs, a new series of 4-(pyrazol-3-yl)[1,2,4]triazolo[3,4-*a*]quinoxaline derivatives were prepared and characterized.

Experimental

M.p.s. were recorded on a Tottoli (Büchi) apparatus and are not corrected. IR (KBr) were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 580B spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) and (DMSO-*d*₆) on Cameca 250 MHz spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. Microanalyses were performed in the microanalytical units, Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Science, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt. Mass spectra were recorded with an LKB model 2091 mass spectrometer and intensities are given in parantheses as a percentage of the base peak.

2-Aroylhydrazino-2-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (3a-f): A solution of 2-chloro-3-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline **2** (0.38 g; 1 mmol) and the desired arylhydrazine (1 mmol) in pure ethanol (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 h, and the reaction mixture was concentrated and left to cool. The de-

sired product that separated was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried. Each product was recrystallized from ethanol as yellow needles. The physical and spectral data of compounds **3a-f** are listed below.

o-Toluoylhydrazino-2-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (**3a**):

Yellow needles, yield: 69%; m.p. 195–196°C (Found: C, 69.47; H, 4.79; N, 18.87. $C_{26}H_{22}N_6O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 69.32; H, 4.92; N, 18.66%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3375 (OH), 3120 (NH), 1680 (OCN); δ (DMSO- d_6): 4.36 (2H, s, CH_2O), 3.14 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.46 (1H, s, NH), 5.24 (1H, s, OH), 7.28–7.84 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.12 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H). MS (m/z): 450 ($M^+ - 1$, 4.45), 450 (22.19), 286 (4.3), 155 (14.3), 143 (8.83), 137 (19.0), 104 (14.1), 102 (25.46), 90 (28.16), 89 (14.0), 78 (20.71), 77 (100), 76 (10.06), 65 (8.92).

2-p-Toluoylhydrazino-2-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (**3b**):

Yellow needles, yield: 76%; m.p. 166–167°C (Found: C, 69.59; H, 4.62; N, 18.38. $C_{26}H_{22}N_6O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 69.32; H, 4.92; N, 18.66%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3420 (OH), 2216 (NH), 1678 (OCN); δ (DMSO- d_6): 4.48 (2H, s, CH_2O), 3.28 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.58 (1H, s, OH), 4.92 (1H, s, NH), 7.21–7.96 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.06 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H). MS (m/z): 457 ($M^+ - 1$, 5.05), 450 (13.99), 432 (20.18), 431 (16.61), 430 (22.13), 356 (10.85), 303 (41.36), 285 (15.81), 284 (17.17), 155 (10.84), 153 (13.79), 143 (21.52), 144 (13.62), 119 (100), 117 (28.02), 104 (16.83), 102 (21.98), 97 (10.55), 77 (80.15).

2-o-Chlorobenzoylhydrazino-2-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (**3c**):

Yellow needles, yield: 62%; m.p. 120–121°C (Found: C, 63.48; H, 4.32; N, 17.94. $C_{25}H_{19}ClN_6O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 63.76; H, 4.07; N, 17.85%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3380 (OH), 3100 (NH), 1672 (CON); δ (DMSO- d_6): 4.12 (2H, s, CH_2O), 4.36 (1H, s, NH), 5.32 (1H, s, OH), 7.14–8.0 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.16 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 9.01 (1H, s, NH). MS (m/z): 472 (5.42), 470 (13.28), 454 (22.19), 452 (53.22), 451 (17.3), 286 (14.3), 155 (12.1), 144 (19.2), 137 (27.4), 113 (8.4), 111 (20.8), 77 (100).

2-p-Nitrobenzoylhydrazino-2-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (**3d**):

Yellow needles, yield: 54%; m.p. 204–205°C (Found: C, 62.08; H, 4.31; N, 20.52. $C_{25}H_{19}N_7O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 62.36; H, 3.98; N, 30.37%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3332 (OH), 3160 (NH), 1649 (CON); δ (DMSO- d_6): 4.48 (2H, s, CH_2O), 4.48 (1H, s,

NH), 5.14 (1H, s, OH), 7.10–7.82 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.31 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 9.14 (1H, s, NH). MS (m/z): 482 ($M^+ - 1$, 12.3), 481 (3.2), 464 (23.4), 430 (11.9), 337 (32.2), 312 (12.8), 282 (24.4), 216 (72.4), 182 (36.2), 85 (41.3), 77 (100).

2-Benzoylhydrazino-3-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (**3e**):

Yellow needles, yield: 84%; m.p. 235–236°C (Found: C, 68.52; H, 4.43; N, 19.48. $C_{25}H_{20}N_6O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 68.79; H, 4.62; N, 19.26%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3210 (OH), 3121 (NH), 1681 (CON); δ (DMSO- d_6): 4.12 (1H, s, NH), 4.52 (2H, s, CH_2O), 5.0 (1H, s, OH), 7.43–8.12 (14H, m, Ar-H), 8.14 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 8.86 (1H, s, NH). MS (m/z): 435 ($M^+ - 1$, 100), 416 (12.3), 403 (36.2), 430 (18.2), 260 (8.8), 173 (14.2), 93 (22.1), 77 (6.2).

2-p-Chlorobenzoylhydrazino-3-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (**3f**):

Yellow needles, yield: 66%; m.p. 224–225°C (Found: C, 63.59; H, 4.32; N, 17.63. $C_{25}H_{19}ClN_6O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 63.76; H, 4.07; N, 17.85%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3420 (OH), 3106 (NH), 1674 (OCN); δ (DMSO- d_6): 4.32 (1H, s, NH), 4.48 (2H, s, CH_2O), 4.89 (1H, s, OH), 7.06–7.94 (14H, m, Ar-H), 8.12 (1H, s, pyrazole 4H), 9.12 (1H, s, NH). MS (m/z): 473 (12.2), 471 (31.14), 456 (6.2), 422 (16.4), 440 (3.9), 430 (2.4), 398 (3.19), 355 (16.35), 352 (2.05), 318 (30.2), 317 (11.96), 311 (15.35), 290 (24.4), 283 (12.75), 236 (14.8), 143 (34.23), 142 (14.3), 129 (34.4), 128 (10.1), 94 (100), 77 (63.7), 57 (49.7).

2-Isonicotinoylhydrazino-2-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (**3g**):

Yellow needles, yield: 91%; m.p. 230–231°C (Found: C, 65.73; H, 4.21; N, 22.53. $C_{25}H_{19}N_7O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 65.89; H, 4.38; N, 22.42%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3216 (OH), 2924 (NH), 1683 (CON); δ (DMSO- d_6): 4.22 (1H, s, NH), 4.32 (2H, s, CH_2O), 4.94 (1H, s, OH), 7.34–8.06 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.24 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 9.0 (1H, s, NH); δ (DMSO- d_6): 4.74 (2H, s, CH_2O), 5.49 (1H, s, OH), 4.81 (1H, s, NH), 7.24–7.93 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.14 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H). MS (m/z): 439 (3.9), 438 (24.5), 437 (90.7), 419 (17.4), 304 (22.7), 303 (100), 295 (90), 103 (10), 78 (19.6), 77 (41.9).

1-Aryl-4-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]-triazolo[4,3-*a*]quinoxaline (**4a-c**): A solution of compound **3** (1 mmol) in *n*-butanol (20 ml) was heated under reflux for 3 h. The mixture was concentrated and left to cool. The desired product that separated out was filtered off, and recrystal-

lized from ethanol chloroform mixture as colorless needles. The physical characters and spectral data of compounds (**4a-c**) are listed below.

1-p-Tolyl-4-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline (4a):

Yield: 66%; m.p. 195–196°C (Found: C, 71.92; H, 4.49; N, 19.58. C₂₆H₂₀N₆O₂ Calcd. for: C, 72.20; H, 4.66; N, 19.43%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 3194 (OH); δ (DMSO-*d*₆): 2.54 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.52 (2H, s, CH₂O), 5.62 (1H, s, OH), 7.36–8.02 (14H, m, Ar-H), 8.08 (1H, s, pyrazole C₄H). MS (*m/z*): 432 (M⁺, 100), 431 (36.3), 401 (32.4), 331 (12.4), 105 (12.4), 77 (43.2).

1-o-Tolyl-4-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline (4b):

Yield: 72%; m.p. 258–269°C (Found: C, 71.92; H, 4.49; N, 19.58. Calcd. for: C, 72.20; H, 4.66; N, 19.43%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 3322 (OH); δ (DMSO-*d*₆): 2.54 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.82 (2H, s, CH₂O), 5.51 (1H, s, OH), 7.38–7.97 (14H, m, Ar-H), 8.24 (1H, s, pyrazole C₄H). MS (*m/z*): 432 (M⁺, 14.2), 431 (32.8), 401 (37.4), 105 (68), 77 (43.2).

1-o-Chlorophenyl-4-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline (4c):

Yield: 61%; m.p. 280–281°C (Found: C, 66.42; H, 3.60; N, 18.24. C₂₅H₁₇ClN₆O₂ Calcd. for: C, 66.29; H, 3.78; N, 18.59%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 3294 (OH); δ (DMSO-*d*₆): 4.66 (2H, s, CH₂O), 5.22 (1H, s, OH), 7.37–8.12 (14H, m, Ar-H), 8.24 (1H, s, pyrazole C₄H). MS (*m/z*): 459 (M⁺+1, 13.4), 453 (10.2), 157 (10.4), 155 (8.12), 134 (12.2), 77 (100).

1-Aryl-4-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline (5a-c): A suspension of compound **4** (0.1 g) in acetic anhydride (10 ml) was boiled under reflux for 1 h. The mixture was then cooled and poured onto crushed ice, and the product separated was filtered off, washed with water, ethanol and dried. Each product was recrystallized from ethanol as colorless needles. The physical and spectral data of compounds **5a-c** are listed below.

1-p-Tolyl-4-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline (5a):

Yield: 84%; m.p. 232–233°C (Found: C, 70.62; H, 4.50; N, 17.52. C₂₈H₂₂N₆O₂ Calcd. for: C, 70.87; H, 4.67; N, 17.71%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1738 (ester C=O), 1593 (C=N); δ (CDCl₃): 2.18 (3H, s, OCOCH₃), 2.46 (3H, s, CH₃), 5.11 (2H, s, CH₂O), 7.04–7.76 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.08 (1H, s, pyrazole

C₄H). MS (*m/z*): 475 (M⁺-1, 2.56), 474 (10.26), 431 (11.68), 431 (8.12), 338 (17.75), 312 (12.36), 311 (21.17), 284 (16.06), 253 (54.88), 213 (10.28), 185 (14.18), 129 (56.14), 115 (14.34), 99 (29.06), 85 (45.15), 95 (24.10), 83 (43.2), 71 (65.0), 40 (100).

1-o-Tolyl-4-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline (5b):

Yield: 66%; m.p. 250–251°C (Found: C, 70.52; H, 4.43; N, 17.98. C₂₈H₂₂N₆O₂ Calcd. for: C, 70.87; H, 4.67; N, 17.71%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1737 (ester C=O), 1595 (C=N); δ (CDCl₃): 2.06 (3H, s, CH₃CO), 4.32 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.89 (2H, s, CH₂O), 7.22–7.88 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.0 (1H, s, pyrazole C₄H). MS (*m/z*): 475 (M⁺+1, 18.2), 474 (M⁺, 74.3), 430 (17.2), 416 (52.4), 384 (17.3), 317 (11.7), 311 (21.2), 284 (18.6), 213 (19.4), 104 (8.2), 90 (100), 77 (32.7).

1-o-Chlorophenyl-4-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline (5c):

Yield: 58%; m.p. > 280°C (Found: C, 65.38; H, 3.64; N, 16.76. C₂₇H₁₉ClN₆O₂ Calcd. for: C, 65.52; H, 3.87; N, 16.92%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 1740 (ester C=O), 1598 (C=N); δ (CDCl₃): 2.03 (3H, s, COCH₃), 5.22 (2H, s, CH₂O), 7.0–7.82 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.16 (1H, s, pyrazole C₄H). MS (*m/z*): 496 (15.1), 494 (40.5), 454 (11.5), 453 (37.5), 452 (32.3), 451 (100), 355 (40.5), 175 (4.3), 143 (6.3), 102 (11.5), 77 (33.8).

2-Hydrazinethiocarboxamide-3-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (6): A suspension of compound **2** (0.1 g, 0.26 mmol) in pure ethanol (30 ml) was treated with thiosemicarbazide (0.27 g, 3 mmol) and heated under reflux for 3 h. It was concentrated and left to cool, and the resulting product was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried (yield: 80 mg, 66%). It was recrystallized from ethanol as colorless needles, m.p. 244–245°C (Found: C, 58.46; H, 4.33; N, 25.29. C₁₉H₁₇SN₇O Calcd. for: C, 58.30; H, 3.38; N, 25.05%); ν_{\max} (cm⁻¹): 3420 (OH), 3120 (NH), (C=S); δ (CDCl₃): 4.82 (2H, s, CH₂O), 4.59 (2H, 6s, NH₂), 5.62 (1H, s, OH), 7.15–7.88 (11H, m, Ar-H), 8.42 (1H, s, pyrazole C₄H), 9.0 (1H, s, NH), 9.22 (1H, s, NH). MS (*m/z*): 392 (M⁺, 12.4), 391 (9.2), 374 (22.92), 360 (31.6), 313 (12.6), 312 (81.6), 219 (40.6), 172 (8.3), 105 (14.3), 77 (100).

2-(1,2-Dihydro-3-methyl-5H, 5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-3-yl)-3-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (7): A solution of compound **6** (0.1 g, 0.3 mmol) in acetic anhydride (10 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 h. The mixture was cooled and poured onto crushed ice, and the product that

separated was filtered off, washed with water and ethanol and dried (yield: 0.1 g; 86%). It was recrystallized from ethanol as pale yellow needles, m.p. 205–206°C (Found: C, 60.11; H, 4.36; N, 21.25. $C_{23}H_{19}SN_7O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 60.39 H, 4.19; N, 21.44%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 1740 (ester C=O); δ ($CDCl_3$): 2.06 (3H, s, $OCOCH_3$), 3.22 (3H, s, CH_3), 5.12 (2H, s, CH_2O), 7.02–7.66 (11H, m, Ar-H), 7.92 (1H, s, NH), 8.12 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H). MS (m/z): 457 (M^+ , 1.2), 356 (30.37), 355 (14.09), 332 (12.12), 290 (16.68), 236 (15.73), 165 (13.44), 163 (10.58), 152 (23.07), 149 (13.0), 137 (24.3), 125 (26.04), 121 (22.8), 111 (42.56), 109 (32.97), 97 (100), 83 (72.38), 79 (20.45), 69 (26.44), 55 (49.92).

2-Alkoxy-3-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline (8a,b): A solution of compound **2** (0.38 g; 1 mmol) in dry ethanol (20 ml) was treated with NaOMe or NaOEt (1 mmol) and heated under reflux for 1 h, and left to cool. The product that separated was filtered off, washed with ethanol and recrystallized from ethanol as colorless needles. The physical and spectral characterization of compounds **8a,b** are listed below.

Compound (8a): Yield: 72%, m.p. 203–204°C (Found: C, 72.30; H, 5.24; N, 17.51. $C_{19}H_{16}N_4O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 72.13; H, 5.10; N, 17.17%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3340 (OH), 1600 (C=N); δ ($DMSO-d_6$): 4.05 (3H, s, CH_3), 4.42 (1H, s, OH), 7.30–8.01 (9H, m, Ar-H), 8.05 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H). MS (m/z): 331 (M^+-1 , 15.9), 304 (23.6), 302 (15.9), 301 (50.3), 273 (20.2), 244 (12.8), 206 (13.8), 198 (20.4), 187 (15.5), 171 (16.9), 169 (12.1), 157 (25.1), 91 (74.8), 78 (26.0), 77 (100), 63 (10.9).

Compound (8b): Yield: 62%, m.p. 264–265°C (Found: C, 69.21; H, 5.34; N, 16.38. $C_{20}H_{18}N_4O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 69.35; H, 5.24; N, 16.18%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3300 (OH), 1597 (C=N); δ ($DMSO-d_6$): 1.32 (3H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_3), 5.22 (2H, q, J 7 Hz, CH_2), 5.40 (1H, s, OH), 7.05–8.20 (9H, m, Ar-H), 8.35 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H). MS (m/z): 345 (M^+-1 , 51.9), 304 (22.6), 302 (15.9), 301 (50.1), 273 (20.2), 244 (12.8), 206 (13.8), 198 (20.4), 187 (15.5), 171 (16.9), 169 (12.1), 157 (25.2), 91 (74.8), 78 (26.0), 77 (100), 63 (10.9).

3-[5-(Hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline 2-formylhydrazone (10a-e): A solution of compound **9** (0.33 g, 1 mmol) in pure ethanol (20 ml) was treated with the desired aldehyde (1 mmol) and few drops of acetic acid, and heated under reflux for 1 h. The mixture was concentrated and left to cool. The product that separated was filtered off, washed

with ethanol and dried. Each product was recrystallized from ethanol in needles. The physical and spectral data of compound **10a-e** are listed below.

Compound (10a): Yield: 68%, m.p. 272–273°C (Found: C, 71.28; H, 4.62; N, 20.14. $C_{25}H_{20}N_6O$ Calcd. for: C, 71.41; H, 4.79; N, 19.99%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3213 (OH), 3122 (NH); δ ($CDCl_3$): 3.49 (1H, s, OH), 4.52 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.92 (1H, s, $CH=N$), 7.32–7.94 (14H, m, Ar-H), 8.02 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 9.12 (1H, s, NH).

Compound (10b): Yield: 62%, m.p. 227–228°C (Found: C, 64.72; H, 4.30; N, 23.24. Calcd. for: C, 64.51; H, 4.11; N, 21.07%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3380 (OH), 3110 (NH); δ ($CDCl_3$): 3.36 (1H, s, OH), 4.60 (2H, s, CH_2O), 6.96 (1H, s, $CH=N$), 7.32–7.84 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.12 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 8.94 (1H, s, NH).

Compound (10c): Yield: 78%, m.p. 224–225°C (Found: C, 69.74; H, 5.32; N, 21.40. $C_{26}H_{25}N_7O$ Calcd. for: C, 69.95; H, 5.44; N, 21.15%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3404 (OH), 3060 (NH); δ ($CDCl_3$): 3.12 (6H, s, $2CH_3$), 3.29 (1H, s, OH), 4.52 (2H, s, CH_2O), 7.02 (1H, s, $CH=N$), 7.36–7.84 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.18 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 9.32 (1H, s, NH).

Compound (10d): Yield: 58%, m.p. 146–147°C (Found: C, 65.71; H, 5.26; N, 16.21. Calcd. for: C, 65.87; H, 5.13; N, 16.46%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3424 (OH), 3092 (NH); δ ($CDCl_3$): 3.84 (1H, s, OH), 3.88–3.94 (9H, 3s, $3OCH_3$), 4.64 (1H, s, CH_2O), 7.28–7.91 (11H, m, Ar-H), 8.06 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 8.68 (1H, $CH=N$), 9.84 (1H, s, NH).

Compound (10e): Yield: 72%, m.p. 245–246°C (Found: C, 68.58; H, 4.43; N, 19.18. $C_{25}H_{20}N_6O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 68.79; H, 4.62; N, 19.26%; ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3406 (OH), 3060 (OH); δ ($CDCl_3$): 4.22 (1H, s, OH), 4.62 (2H, s, CH_2O), 4.72 (1H, s, OH), 7.38–7.88 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.04 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 8.32 (1H, s, $CH=N$), 9.38 (1H, s, NH).

1-Aryl-4-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]-triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline (11a-c): A solution of compound **10** (1 mmol) in pure ethanol (20 ml) was treated with $FeCl_3$ (1 g) and the mixture was heated under reflux for 1 h, and left to cool. The resulting product was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried. Each product was recrystallized from ethanol in needles. The physical and spectral data for compounds (**11a-c**) are listed below.

Compound (11a): Yield: 70%, m.p. 192–193°C (Found: C, 64.56; H, 3.58; N, 21.36. $C_{25}H_{17}N_7O_3$ Calcd. for: C, 64.78;

H, 3.70; N, 21.16%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3380 (OH), 1599 (C=N); δ (CDCl_3): 4.52 (2H, s, CH_2O), 5.42 (1H, s, OH), 7.22–7.79 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.12 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H).

Compound (11b): Yield: 50%, m.p. 220–221°C (Found: C, 66.31; H, 4.50; N, 16.29. $\text{C}_{28}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4$ Calcd. for: C, 66.13; H, 4.76; N, 16.53%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3410 (OH), 1598 (C=N); δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 4.12 (1H, s, OH), 4.39 (2H, s, CH_2O), 7.22–7.84 (11H, m, Ar-H), 8.18 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H). MS (m/z): 509 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$, 100), 503 (2.4), 478 (7.5), 317 (16.14), 281 (10.7), 261 (5.6), 104 (11.2), 102 (12.8), 78 (25.2), 77 (100), 76 (15), 69 (13.7), 63 (14.3).

Compound (11c): Yield: 64%, m.p. 215–216°C (Found: C, 69.31; H, 4.28; N, 19.52. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_8\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$ Calcd. for: C, 69.11; H, 4.18; N, 19.34%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3313 (OH), 1594 (C=N); δ ($\text{DMSO}-d_6$): 4.12 (1H, s, OH), 4.58 (2H, s, CH_2O), 7.42–7.81 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.41 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 9.21 (1H, s, OH). MS (m/z): 434 (M^+ , 100), 417 (12.1), 403 (22.2), 341 (16.6), 261 (8.4), 173 (14.3), 97 (21.2), 77 (8.2).

1-Aryl-4-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]-triazolo[4,3-a]quinoxaline (12a-c): Obtained from (11a-c) as described for the synthesis of 5. The physical and spectral data for compounds (12a-c) are listed below.

Compound (12a): Yield: 48%, m.p. 260–261°C (Found: C, 64.43; H, 3.49; N, 19.52. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_7\text{O}_4$ Calcd. for: C, 64.15; H, 3.79; N, 19.40%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 1740 (ester C=O), 1599 (C=N); δ (CDCl_3): 2.12 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 4.32 (2H, s, CH_2O), 7.30–7.92 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.22 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H).

Compound (12b): Yield: 63%, m.p. 142–143°C (Found: C, 65.26; H, 4.52; N, 15.30. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$ Calcd. for: C, 65.44; H, 4.76; N, 15.27%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 1745 (ester C=O), 1600 (C=N); δ (CDCl_3): 2.12 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 4.12 (2H, s, CH_2O), 3.16–3.22 (9H, 3s, 3OCH_3), 7.32–7.89 (11H, m, Ar-H), 8.06 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H).

Compound (12c): Yield: 70%, m.p. 158–159°C (Found: C, 68.23; H, 4.42; N, 17.49. $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3$ Calcd. for: C, 68.06; H, 4.23; N, 17.64%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 1739 (ester C=O), 1600 (C=N); δ (CDCl_3): 2.14 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 4.63 (1H, s, OH), 7.12–7.94 (13H, m, Ar-H), 8.16 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H).

β -Naphthylglyoxal-3-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline hydrazone (13): A solution of 2-hydrazino-3-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline 9 (1 g, 3 mmol) in pure ethanol (20 ml) was treated with β -naphthylglyoxal (0.74 g, 4 mmol) and heated under

reflux for 3 h. The mixture was concentrated and left to cool, the collected solid was filtered off, washed with ethanol and dried (1 g, 66%). It was recrystallized from ethanol in needles, m.p. 238–239°C (Found: C, 72.02; H, 4.35; N, 16.61. $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2$ Calcd. for: C, 72.27; H, 4.45; N, 16.86%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3360 (OH), 3120 (NH), 1740 (C=O); δ (CDCl_3): 4.56 (1H, s, OH), 5.59 (2H, s, CH_2O), 7.41 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.46–8.0 (16H, m, Ar-H), 8.4 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 8.12 (1H, s, NH). MS (m/z): 499 ($\text{M}^+ + 1$, 2.3), 498 (M^+ , 16.24), 481 (6.32), 467 (16.2), 256 (9.12), 225 (36.4), 214 (18.82), 173 (8.24), 129 (44.2), 94 (100), 86 (12.4), 77 (16.21), 74 (21.32), 66 (10.1), 60 (18.2), 57 (36.4).

β -Naphthylglyoxal-3-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline-N-acetylhydrazone (14): A solution of 13 (50 mg, 0.1 mmol) in acetic anhydride (5 ml) was heated under reflux for 1 h. The mixture was allowed to cool and poured onto crushed ice, and the product was filtered off, washed with water and ethanol and dried (40 mg, 60%). It was recrystallized from ethanol as colorless needles, m.p. 156–157°C (Found: C, 69.84; H, 4.38; N, 14.62. $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_6\text{O}_7$ Calcd. for: C, 70.09; H, 4.50; N, 14.43%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 1741 (ester C=O), 1663 (OCN); δ (CDCl_3): 2.08 (3H, s, OCOCH_3), 2.32 (3H, s, NCOCH_3), 5.12 (2H, s, CH_2O), 7.32–8.10 (16H, m, Ar-H), 8.18 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 8.82 (1H, s, CH=N). MS (m/z): 582 (M^+ , 11.2), 541 (1.5), 253 (12.07), 256 (5.24), 213 (10.35), 129 (40.81), 113 (10.4), 94 (100), 87 (16.84), 84 (18.45), 74 (24.47), 73 (58.11), 66 (22.39), 60 (30.75).

Ethyl-2-oxobutyrates-3-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline hydrazone (15): A mixture of compound 9 (0.33 g, 1 mmol) in pure ethanol (20 ml) was treated with ethylacetoacetate (10 ml) and heated on a water bath at 60°C for 2 h. The mixture was evaporated under reduced pressure and the collected solid was recrystallized from ethanol as yellow needles, yield 68%, m.p. 190–191°C (Found: C, 64.72; H, 5.30; N, 18.69. $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{24}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3$ Calcd. for: C, 64.85; H, 5.44; N, 18.91%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3320 (OH), 3120 (NH), 1725 (ester C=O), 1600 (C=N); δ (CDCl_3): 1.32 (3H, t, J 7.4 Hz, CH_3), 1.96 (3H, s, $\text{CH}_3\text{C}=\text{N}$), 3.52 (2H, s, CH_2O), 3.82 (1H, s, OH), 4.10 (2H, q, J 7.4 Hz, CH_2), 4.52 (2H, s, CH_2), 7.10–7.82 (9H, m, Ar-H), 8.02 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H), 11.32 (1H, s, NH). MS (m/z): 550 (M^+ , 4.7), 442 (15.1), 431 (100), 414 (10.2), 394 (11.09), 378 (16.1), 352 (33.5), 351 (65.9), 302 (17.7), 300 (34.1), 271 (24.2), 186 (19.0), 130 (36.6), 88 (35.5), 82 (44.8), 76 (8.7), 60 (89.9).

3-[5-(Hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]-2-(1,2-dihydro-3-methyl-3H-pyrazol-3-one) quinoxaline (**16**): A solution of compound **9** (0.33 g, 1 mmol) in pure ethanol (20

ml) was treated with ethylacetoacetate (5 ml) and heated under reflux for 6 h. The mixture was evaporated under diminished pressure, and the solid collected was crystallized

Scheme 1

Reagents and conditions: (a) POCl_3 , 70°C , 1 h; (b) ArCONHNH_2 , EtOH, Δ , 1 h; (c) BuOH, Δ , 1 h; (d) Ac_2O , Δ , 1 h; (e) $\text{NH}_2\text{NHCSNH}_2$, EtOH, Δ , 1 h; (f) Ac_2O , Δ , 1 h; (g) RONA.

Scheme 2

Reagents and conditions: (a) $\text{NH}_2\text{-NH}_2$, EtOH, Δ , 1 h; (b) ArCHO , EtOH, H^+ , Δ , 1 h; (c) FeCl_3 , EtOH, Δ , 1 h; (d) Ac_2O , Δ , 1 h; (e) Ac_2O , Δ , 1 h; (f) $\text{CH}_3\text{COCH}_2\text{COOEt}$, EtOH, 60°C ; (g) Ac_2O , Δ , 1 h.

from ethanol as orange needles (yield, 0.2 g; 50%), m.p. > 270°C (Found: C, 66.18; H, 4.36; N, 20.57. $C_{22}H_{18}N_6O_2$ Calcd. for: C, 66.32; H, 4.55; N, 21.10%); ν_{\max} (cm^{-1}): 3309 (OH), 3108 (NH), 1596 (C=N); δ ($CDCl_3$): 1.42 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.68 (2H, s, CH_2O), 8.12 (1H, s, pyrazole C_4H) 12.20 (1H, s, exchangeable NH). MS (m/z): 399 (26.55), 257 (6.67), 318 (22.87), 317 (80.54), 303 (26.55), 290 (14.14), 289 (15.91), 286 (12.93), 143 (25.14), 129 (14.68), 117 (13.15), 102 (21.98), 90 (31.15), 77 (100), 76 (30.05).

Results and discussion

As many of N-heterocyclic compounds derived from carbohydrates are therapeutically active, we are interested to synthesise N-heterocycles from carbohydrate precursors. We have demonstrated the synthesis of different heterocycles including pyrazoles, triazoles, imidazoles and isoxazoles from dehydro-L-ascorbic acid and its analogs⁶⁻¹⁰. Thus, when dehydro-L-ascorbic acid (L-threo-2,3-hexodiulosono-1,4-lactone) was treated with *o*-phenylenediamine and phenylhydrazine, it gave the quinoxaline hydrazone which upon treatment with boiling acetic anhydride, dehydration of the alditol portion took place with simultaneous ring closure to give the quinoxaline pyrazole¹¹ **1** that was transformed to 2-chloroderivative upon treatment with $POCl_3$ ¹². Treatment of **2** with aroylhydrazine in ethanol, afforded the corresponding yellow compounds **3a-c**, whose structures were elucidated from their IR, mass and elemental analysis. Boiling of compounds **3a-c** in butanol for long time, afforded 1-aryl-4-[5-(hydroxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl][1,2,4]triazolo[4,3-*a*]quinoxalines **4a-c** which upon acetylation with boiling acetic anhydride, afforded the acetyl derivatives **5a-c**. Treatment of compound **2** with thiosemicarbazide, afforded the hydrazone **6** which upon acetylation with boiling acetic anhydride, afforded compound **7**, namely, 2-(1,2-dihydro-3-methyl-5(1*H*)-5-thio-1,2,4-triazol-2-yl)-3-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]quinoxaline whose structure was confirmed by its spectral data. Also, treatment of **2** with sodium methoxide or sodium ethoxide, gave compounds **8a,b**. Furthermore, treatment of **2** with hydrazine hydrate, afforded the 2-hydrazino derivative **9**, which upon treatment with substituted aldehydes, afforded compounds **10a-e** which were converted into the triazoloquinoxalines **11a-c** upon oxidation with ferric chloride. Heating of **11a-c** with acetic anhydride led to the formation of the acetyl derivatives **12a-c**. Treatment of **9** with β -naphthylglyoxal, gave compound **13** which upon acetyla-

tion, gave the diacetyl derivative **14**. Furthermore, treatment of the hydrazinoquinoxaline **9** with ethylacetoacetate, gave compound **15** which upon acetylation with boiling acetic anhydride, gave compound **16**, namely, 3-[5-(acetoxymethyl)-1-phenylpyrazol-3-yl]-2-[1,2-dihydro-5-methyl-3*H*-pyrazol-3-one]quinoxaline whose structure was confirmed by spectral data.

Biological Screening:

Quinoxaline itself is mainly of academic interest as the quinoxaline derivatives are used as dyes, pharmaceuticals, and antibiotics such as olaquinox, carbadox, echinomycin, and actinoleutin (Fig. 1). It is also used as antitumoral agents¹³.

Fig. 1. Approved marketed drugs with structure.

Determination of antimicrobial activity:

Cultures of five different microorganisms, namely *C. albicans*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *E. coli* and *Ps. aeruginosa*, were used to investigate the antimicrobial activities of the synthesized compounds. The antimicrobial activities were assayed biologically using diffusion plate technique. The experiments were carried out by mixing spore suspension

106 colon forming units (CFU) per mL of the test strain and 75 mL of nutrient agar medium at 45°C. The mixture was then poured into a 15 cm sterile metallic Petri plate. The medium was allowed to solidify, and 8 mm wells were dug with a sterile metallic borer, then a DMF solution of the test sample (1 mL) at 1 mg/mL was added to the respective wells. DMF was served as negative control, and the standard antimicrobial drugs Ciprofloxacin and Clotrimazole are used as positive control. The layer was allowed to set for 30 min and incubated at optimum incubation temperature $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$.

Test organism growth may be affected by the inhibitory action of the test compound, and so, a clear zone around the disc appeared as an indication of the inhibition of the test organism growth. The size of clearing zone is proportional to the inhibitory action of the test compound. Measurements were considered after 72 h for fungi and 24 h for bacteria.

Antimicrobial activity:

Structure-activity relationship (SAR) plays an important role in the study of the activities of synthesized compounds of quinoxaline nucleus (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Quinoxaline nucleus.

In this study we developed a simple and reproducible technique for synthesis of various pyrazolyl quinoxaline derivatives by connecting the pyrazolyl moiety at 2 position of the quinoxaline nucleus with short reaction time, excellent yields, and without formation of undesirable side products. The antimicrobial activity of the synthesized compounds was evaluated. Some of our compounds were tested for antimicrobial activity against five test organisms: *Candida albicans*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* using Ciprofloxacin and Clotrimazole (10 µg/disc) as standard drugs. The agar well diffusion method¹⁴ was used for studying the potential activities of these compounds. Representative compounds showed significant activity in antimicrobial screen as zone of inhibition (mm) that showed inhibition zones >10 which is depicted in Table 1.

Antifungal activity:

The aromaticity of the phenyl or heterocyclic rings decrease the activity against *C. albicans*, higher activities were noticed for compounds **6** and **15** against *Candida albicans*. On the other hand, compounds **7** showed loss of some antimicrobial (antifungal) activities against the tested microorganisms that may indicate the cyclization of the hydrazone moiety of compounds **6** and **15** to 2-(1-pyrazolyl)-quinoxalines¹⁵.

Table 1. Antimicrobial activities^a of some synthesized compounds

Tested microorganism Compd. No.	Gram-positive bacteria				Gram-negative bacteria				Fungi	
	S		B		Ps		E		C	
	DMF	Cpd.	DMF	Cpd.	DMF	Cpd.	DMF	Cpd.	DMF	Cpd.
3a	12	12	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
3f	11	11	10	10	11	11	11	11	11	11
5a	10	10	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
6	11	11	11	11	10	10	11	11	12	12
7	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	10	10
8a	12	12	10	10	11	11	10	10	11	11
9	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
10b	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11
13	12	12	12	12	12	12	10	10	11	11
15	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	11	12	12
Ciprofloxacin	9	30	9	0	9	30	9	30	–	–
Clotrimazole	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	–	10	17

^aMean zone of inhibition in mm.

S – *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC6538P, B – *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC19659, Ps – *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC9027, E – *Escherichia coli* ATCC8739, C – *Candida albicans* ATCC2091.

Antibacterial activity:

Comparing **3a** to **5a** we found there are loss of some antibacterial activity at **5a** which may indicate cyclization of the hydrazone moiety of compounds **3a** to **5a**. Comparing **13** to the others we find that **13** has higher antibacterial activity than the others which may indicate the cyclization of hydrazone moiety and hence a loss in antibacterial activity was observed.

Conclusion

This work demonstrates a rapid and efficient method for the synthesis of new heterocyclic compounds like triazolo- and pyrazol-3-yl-quinoxaline derivatives from L-ascorbic acid derivatives (The well known and cheap compound). All the synthesized compounds are characterized by spectral data (IR, ¹H NMR, Mass) and the structures were in consistent with the data. Some of the synthesized compounds were tested for their antimicrobial activity against five tested organisms.

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